

STUDIES ON AERIAL OXIDATION OF COAL WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE DISTRIBUTION OF OXYGEN AND CARBON IN COAL AND ITS OXIDATION PRODUCTS.

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Bituminous coking coal samples have been subjected to aerial oxidation at 150° for different periods of time and quantitative distribution of carbon has been investigated in the oxidation products by estimating oxygen in relative groups e.g., OH, CO, COOH.

Coal is an organic colloidal complex which may be resolved into three principal classes of substances, viz. (a) bitumen, soluble in organic solvents, (b) humic acids, insoluble in organic solvents but susceptible to oxidation and (c) resistant organic complex, insoluble in organic solvents and resistant to chemical reactions. The bitumens and resistant portions together form only a small fraction of coal. The key to the solution of the difficult problem of constitution of coal is held by the humic acid constituent which constitutes 70-80% of the coal substance.

Very little humic acid can, however, be obtained from mature bituminous coal by treatment with alkali. Evidently the condensation and polymerisation processes involved in the formation of coal have gone very far to form almost insoluble products in these coals. It is, however, found that by careful oxidation, these humic acids may be made soluble in alkali and obtained as regenerated humic acid. As a result of various oxidation and other experiments, it has been suggested by several workers that this regenerated humic acid is constituted mainly of aromatic ring-compounds, condensed together to form a complex nucleus which is associated with outer groupings or side-chains. In the course of oxidation, the outer groupings are first oxygenated giving rise to carboxylic compounds soluble in alkali, which are recovered as regenerated humic acid. The nucleus may be disintegrated by further careful oxidation giving rise to aromatic carboxylic acids, oxalic acid etc., while by too drastic an oxidation, the final products of combustion such as H_2O , CO_2 , and CO may be obtained.

In the present investigation, we have studied a sample of bituminous coking coal obtained from Talcher Colliery. Its chemical composition can be expressed by the empirical formula $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ (calculated on moisture, ash, ammonia, and H_2S free basis). As the amount of humic acid obtained by alkali treatment is very small (2.20%), we have subjected it to careful oxidation by air at 150° for different periods of time and have tried to follow the distribution of carbon quantitatively in the oxidation products and

estimated the oxygen contained in reactive groups such as carboxyl, hydroxyl (both phenolic and alcoholic), carbonyl and methoxyl in the original and in the oxidised coal. As carbon and next to it oxygen are the most important elements in coal, it is desirable to trace how these elements are distributed in coal and its oxidation products. This may also throw some light on the mechanism of oxidation of coal on which considerable difference of opinion exists.

Analysis of coal.

Proximate analysis (on dry basis).		Ultimate analysis (on dry ash-free basis).		
Per cent.		Per cent.	Ratio.	
Moisture	... 10.04	C	... 81.34	
Ash	... 7.49	H	... 5.28	C/H=15.7
Volatile matter	... 37.14	N	... 1.76	C/O=7.26
Fixed carbon	... 55.37	S	... 0.52	
		O	... 11.20 (by diff.)	

Rational analysis.

(a) Using pyridine as solvent.		(b) Using benzene as solvent.	
	Per cent.		Per cent.
α -Fraction (pyridine insoluble)	... 81.50	Bitumen (benzene soluble)	... 10.54
β -Fraction (pyridine soluble but chloroform insoluble)	... 10.67	Humic matter (obtained by air oxidation)	... 77.09
γ -Fraction (pyridine and chloroform soluble)	... 7.83	Resistant residues	... 12.37

In the above data, α -fraction indicates the resistant portion of coal together with insoluble humic acids, while the β - and γ -fractions indicate the amount of bitumen including some humic matter. As pyridine is a basic substance and is liable to dissolve some of the humic acid, we have resolved coal into different fractions by using benzene in the place of pyridine and subjecting the benzene-insoluble coal to air oxidation at 150° for 192 hours followed by alkali treatment.

Progressive Oxidation of Coal by Air at 150°.

The stepwise oxidation of coal has proved to be one of the most fruitful methods of exploring the composition and ultimate structure of coal. Aerial oxidation of coal has been studied extensively by Wheeler, Kreulen, Fischer and others (Kreulen, *Brennstoff-Chem.*, 1927, 8, 241; Fischer and co-workers, *ibid.*, 1932, 13, 1933; Francis and Wheeler, *Safety in Mines Res. Board*, Paper No. 27, 1926). Other slightly stronger oxidising agents

such as nitric acid (Smith and Howard, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 512, 2322), hydrogen peroxide (Francis and Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2236), alkaline permanganate (Bone and co-workers, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1930, A, 217, 480), acid permanganate (Francis, *Fuel*, 1938, 17, 363), chlorine peroxide (*J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. News Ed.*, 1940, 3, 1), pressure oxidation in alkaline solution (Fischer and Schrader, *Ges. Abh. Kennt. Khole*, 1920, 5, 200, 500) and even electrolytic oxidation (Lynch and Collett, *Fuel*, 1932, 11, 408) have been used by a large number of workers.

Aerial oxidation of coal under controlled conditions differs from the oxidation by other reagents in that no profound structural changes are likely to result by the former process. The peripheral groups are mainly affected and replaced by COOH groups.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the present investigation, oxidation of coal was carried out at a temperature of 150°-160° with air, freed from CO₂, blown by means of a Cenco-blower continuously for about 12 days through finely divided coal placed in the middle of a glass combustion tube heated in an electric furnace. After every 12 hours, the tube was taken out, the coal inside was well stirred and the tube replaced. Test samples were taken out periodically and the yield of humic acid was determined by using 4% sodium hydroxide as the solvent. Humic acid was precipitated from the solution by dilute hydrochloric acid, thoroughly washed, and dried in vacuum at 80°

TABLE I.

Air oxidation of coal at 150°.

Oxidation time.	in Solubility 4% NaOH.	Humic acid re- covered from alkali soln	subs- Soluble tances.	Oxidation time.	in Solubility 4% NaOH.	Humic acid re- covered from alkali soln.	subs- Soluble tances.
0 hr.	2'20%	0%	2'20%	168 hr.	87'04%	63'58%	23'46%
24	25'47	17'83	7'64	192	87'63	62'09	25'54
48	42'08	31'90	10'18	216	87'03	60'50	26'53
72	60'95	47'62	13'33	240	86'69	58'12	28'57
96	72'88	56'28	16'60	264	85'25	57'23	28'02
120	81'16	60'65	21'51	288	84'72	55'54	29'18
144	85'36	63'61	21'75				

It appears from Table I that (i) alkali solubility of oxidised coal gradually increases and reaches a maximum after 192 hours and then gradually decreases, (ii) the yield of water-insoluble humic acid reaches a maximum after about 144 hours and then slowly decreases, (iii) yield of water-soluble oxidation products increases continually with the progress of oxidation. Oxalic acid and benzoquinone have been found to be present in water-soluble products and carbon dioxide in the gaseous products of oxidation.

The process of oxidation has also been followed by determination of the weight of oxidised coal and its carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur contents which are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II.

Change in the weight and composition of coal.

Oxidation time.	Increase or decrease in wt.	% Composition		
		C.	H.	O, N and S.
0 hr.	0	81.34	5.18	13.48
24	2.95%	79.01	5.53	15.46
48	5.51	76.97	5.23	17.80
72	7.94	75.18	4.90	19.95
96	7.93	74.34	4.67	20.99
120	6.66	72.84	4.38	22.78
144	4.51	72.54	4.01	23.45
168	2.01	71.99	3.85	24.16
192	-0.52	71.56	3.65	24.76
216	-2.03	70.70	3.46	25.84
240	-3.34	70.01	3.36	26.63
264	-4.21	69.63	3.23	27.14
288	-5.18	69.15	3.13	27.72

From the above table it will be observed that the oxidation of coal may be divided into three distinct periods. In the first, there is an increase in the weight of coal, in the second, there is an equilibrium in the increase in weight due to fixation of oxygen and loss due to escape of gaseous products of oxidation, and in the third there is a gradual increase in the loss of weight. Thus on the one hand, there is formation of humic acid in gradually increasing amounts due to absorption of oxygen and on the other hand there is decomposition of humic acid so formed. Up to 144 hours, the rate of formation of humic acids predominates over the rate of decomposition. After that period, the decomposition of humic acids predominates. The

percentage of carbon and hydrogen steadily decreases with the progress of oxidation, while that of oxygen (including nitrogen and sulphur) gradually increases, the increase being more than double in course of 12 days. The higher hydrogen content observed after 24 and 42 hours of oxidation is perhaps due to incomplete removal of moisture from the hygroscopic products. Considering the increase or decrease in weight of oxidised coal and its composition, it is possible to find out the amounts of carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen present in the oxidised coal and to compare these amounts with the percentages present in the original coal. Any decrease in carbon and hydrogen contents is due to the loss of CO_2 and H_2O , while the increase in oxygen content is due to addition of oxygen to the coal substance. These will be clear from the following data calculated from Table II.

TABLE III.

Amounts of C, H and O present in oxidised coal.

Oxidation time.	Amounts of different elements present in oxidised coal on the basis of 100 g. original coal.			Loss or gain of different elements.		
	C.	H.	O, N and S.	C.	H.	O, N and S.
0 hr.	81.34 g.	5.18 g.	13.48 g.	0%	0%	0%
24	81.30	—	15.92	- 0.05	—	+ 18.10
48	81.21	—	18.78	- 0.16	—	+ 39.32
72	81.08	—	21.54	- 0.32	—	+ 59.89
96	80.23	5.04	22.19	- 1.36	—	+ 64.68
120	77.67	4.67	24.30	- 4.51	- 9.82	+ 81.27
144	75.78	4.19	24.50	- 6.83	- 19.09	+ 81.79
168	73.41	3.93	24.64	- 9.76	- 24.11	+ 82.79
192	71.19	3.66	24.63	- 12.47	- 29.31	+ 82.78
216	69.26	3.39	25.31	- 14.85	- 34.56	+ 87.91
240	67.83	3.17	25.74	- 16.62	- 38.80	+ 90.95
264	66.70	3.09	25.99	- 18.00	- 40.35	+ 92.80
288	65.58	2.97	26.28	- 19.36	- 42.66	+ 94.85

Table III indicates that the rate of removal of hydrogen is greater than that of carbon. The loss of carbon and hydrogen is due to the escape of CO_2 and H_2O . The amount of CO_2 escaping up to 4 days is very small (1.36% only) though the amount of oxygen found in the oxidised coal rapidly increases to about 65%. A critical state of oxidation is apparently reached at this stage and further additions of oxygen are accompanied by

increase in the loss of carbon as CO_2 and hydrogen as H_2O . About 20% of carbon and over 40% of hydrogen of the coal are removed in course of 12 days.

Distribution of Oxygen in Coal and in Humic Acid obtained from Oxidised Coal.

It will be observed that in the course of oxidation, the oxygen content of coal increased from 11.2% to about 25.5%. In order to see how this oxygen is distributed in the form of oxygen-containing groups such as carboxyl, hydroxyl, methoxyl and carbonyl, these radicals were quantitatively determined in coal and in humic acid obtained from oxidised coal. Analysis of samples of humic acid extracted from different stages of oxidised coal indicated a fair degree of constancy of composition (Table IV). This constancy is achieved after 144 hours of oxidation with an oxygen content of about 36%. A critical state is reached at this stage, and further oxidation breaking down the humic acid into carbon dioxide and water. It is interesting to note that no nitrogen or sulphur is lost by this oxidation as practically the whole of sulphur in the original coal is found in the humic acid.

TABLE IV.

Composition of the recovered humic acids.

Hours of oxidation of coal.	Yield of humic acid.	Composition of humic acid		
		C	H.	O (including N and S).
48	31.90%	62.02%	3.06%	34.92%
144	63.61	60.98	2.98	36.01
192	63.58	61.01	3.00	35.99
288	55.54	60.03	2.97	37.00

Determination of Carboxyl and Hydroxyl Groups.—The usual method for the determination of carboxyl and total hydroxyl is to methylate the product exhaustively and then to find out the total methoxyl by Zeisel's method and the ester methoxyl by saponification. The ether methoxyl is then found out by difference. But methylation by means of methyl alcohol and hydrochloric acid has been found to be incomplete. Diazomethane, though somewhat better, has also been found to cause incomplete methylation by several workers, due probably to steric hindrance found in several aromatic acids. We have, therefore, followed the following three methods which have been found by Ubaedini (*Brennstoff. Chem.*, 1930, 18, 273) to give satisfactory results.

(I) Total COOH and phenolic OH were found out by titration with alkali under the following conditions.

Humic acid was treated with excess of alcoholic $N/5$ KOH (using 95% alcohol), when potassium humate, formed by neutralisation of COOH and phenolic OH groups, precipitated. It was filtered off and the excess of alkali in the filtrate was titrated using phenolphthalein as indicator. This gives the amount of alkali required to neutralise the total carboxylic and phenolic OH groups.

Phenolic OH group was then determined separately as follows:—

The above precipitate of potassium humate was suspended in alcohol and a stream of carbon dioxide was passed through it when free phenolic groups were liberated according to the following reaction,

The strength of alcohol was carefully regulated so as not to fall below 75%. Under these conditions potassium humate containing free phenolic groups remained insoluble while K_2CO_3 went into solution. This was filtered and washed with 75% alcohol. Estimation of potassium carbonate in the filtrate gave figures for phenolic OH (method *a*), while estimation of potassium in the precipitate gave figure for carboxyl groups (method *b*).

(a) The amount of potassium carbonate in the filtrate was determined by adding excess of acid and titrating back the excess with $N/10$ -KOH. (Direct titration of the carbonate solution was not possible owing to light yellow colour of the filtrate). The value of phenolic OH was obtained directly from amount of potassium carbonate found and that of carboxyl was found by difference.

(b) Carboxyl group was also determined directly by collecting the precipitate of potassium humate containing free phenolic group in a platinum crucible and gently igniting the same to ash. The alkali (K_2O) in the ash was estimated by titration. This alkali gave the amount of carboxyl groups present in humic acids. Phenolic OH was found by difference.

(II) In the second process, carboxyl groups were estimated directly by treating humic acid with a solution of calcium acetate when calcium humate was formed and free acetic acid liberated.

In order to complete this reaction, it was necessary to remove the free

acetic acid as soon as it was formed. This was done by adding finely powdered calcium carbonate according to the following reaction,

The carbon dioxide evolved in the above reaction was swept forward by air, free from carbon dioxide and estimated by absorption in caustic potash bulbs. It will be seen that one molecule of carbon dioxide is equivalent to two carboxyl groups in the humic acid.

(III) The total OH groups (both phenolic and alcoholic) present in the substance were estimated by acetylating with acetic anhydride and pyridine. By deducting the phenolic OH, found by the previous methods, the value of alcoholic OH was obtained. The data are given in the following table.

TABLE V.

Method of estimation.	Humic acid				Coal			
	Hydroxyl groups.			Carboxyl.	Hydroxyl groups.			Carboxyl.
	Total.	Phenolic	Alc.		Total	Phenolic	Alc.	
I (a)	...	6.32%	...	24.06%	...	0.093%	...	5.01%
I (b)	...	6.11	...	25.39	...	0.12	...	4.23
II	...	...	...	23.08	...	...	...	0.88
III	6.41%	6.21	0.20%	...	2.08%	0.11	1.97%	...

The above data show that fairly concordant values are obtained for humic acids but not for coal. Too small values are obtained in the case of coal particularly by method II, due presumably to incomplete reaction between the insoluble coal substance and calcium acetate. Hence only a small fraction of total oxygen in coal can be accounted for (Table VII).

Estimation of Carbonyl Groups.—Carbonyl groups have been estimated by treatment with phenylhydrazine, the excess of which is determined by means of Fehling's solution. The precipitated cuprous oxide was collected and estimated by titration with potassium permanganate (Strache and Harrancourt, *Brennstoff-Chem.*, 1924, B, 350). The amounts of carbonyl groups found in humic acid and coal are 3.54% and 0.12% respectively. No methoxyl groups have been detected either in coal or in humic acid.

Oxygen Balance of Humic Acid and Coal.

From the above data it is possible to calculate the amount of oxygen found in various reactive groups in the coal substance and in the humic acids examined. The following table collated from the previous data gives an idea of the oxygen in the various groups,

TABLE VI.

Reactive groups	Humic acid		Coal	
	Amount.	Fraction of total oxygen.	Amount.	Fraction of total oxygen.
Total oxygen	32.87%	—	11.2%	—
Oxygen in COOH	16.98	51.6%	0.633	5.65%
.. .. phenolic OH	6.03	18.3	0.1	0.888
.. .. alcoholic OH	—	—	1.85	16.52
.. .. CO group	2.02	6.14	0.07	0.62
Oxygen accounted	25.04	76.04	2.67	23.77
.. unaccounted	7.83	23.96	8.53	76.23

It will be found that 76.04% of the total oxygen in humic acid have been accounted for, while the amount of oxygen accounted for in coal amounts to 23.77% only. The unaccounted oxygen is apparently due to stable ether or cyclic oxygen. The presence of such stable oxygen linkage has also been suggested by other investigators (Kaschagen, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1937, 29, 600; Fischer and Eisner, *ibid.*, 1371).

From the above data it is possible to get an idea regarding the process of aerial oxidation of coal. The major portion of oxygen in oxidised coal is found in -COOH- groups. It will be seen from previous data that the COOH groups in coal increased from 4.7% to 24.8%, phenolic OH from 0.11% to 6.28% and the ketonic (CO) groups from 0.12% to 3.54% in the course of oxidation. Apparently the external groupings in coal are oxidised giving place to carboxyl groups and the phenolic (OH) and ketonic (CO) groups are also considerably increased. Surprisingly, however, no increase in the alcoholic OH groups has been found during oxidation. On the contrary a slight decrease from 1.97% to 0.2% was observed. It is likely that alcoholic groups are immediately further oxidised giving rise to carboxyl groups.

Equivalent Weight of Humic Acid.—100 G. of humic acid contain 3.54 g. i.e., 0.126 mol. of CO (Table VI). Hence for at least one CO group in humic acid per molecule, the equivalent weight becomes 800.

As 100 g. of humic acid contain 24.8 g. or 0.55 mol. of COOH and 6.21 g. of phenolic OH i.e., 0.375 mol., the ratio of carbonyl, hydroxyl and carboxyl groups in the humic acid molecule becomes 2:6:9 and its molecular weight becomes 1600.

Distribution of Carbon in the Oxidation Products of Coal.

Determination of the yield and carbon content of various products obtained after 144 and 192 hours of oxidation enabled us to determine quantitatively how carbon is affected in the course of oxidation. The gaseous product

(i.e. CO_2) was determined by absorption in potash bulbs, while the oxidised coal was resolved into different fractions by treatment with 4% alkali and acidification of the filtrate. Carbon content of solid products was determined by combustion, while that of the solution by oxidation with potassium dichromate. The distribution of carbon in various fractions is given below.

TABLE VII.

		Carbon content after oxidation for	
		144 hours.	192 hours.
Carbon as CO_2	...	6.37%	9.37%
as water-soluble organic compounds	...	24.39	33.52
as humic acids	...	54.8	45.56
resistant residues (i.e. not dissolved in 4% alkali)		12.50	10.37
unaccounted	...	1.40	2.02

Mechanism of Aerial Oxidation.—It will be observed that in the course of oxidation, the oxygen content of the oxidised coal slowly increased by more than 100% and carbon dioxide was evolved at the same time. The increase in oxygen content is mostly due to the formation of humic and water-soluble acids. If the view that the coal consists of a nuclear complex of condensed aromatic rings with side-chains be accepted, it may be visualised that oxygen first enters the side-chain forming alcoholic groups which are unstable and quickly disappear giving place to carboxyl groups. As a result practically no alcoholic group can be detected in humic acid. The chemical composition of humic acid consisting of carboxyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups and perhaps one ketonic group remains practically constant. The yield of humic acid increases with the progress of oxidation but after 144 hours slowly decreases while the yield of water-soluble acids increases continuously. Evidently in humic acid, the side-chains have been replaced by carboxyl and new phenolic groups have been formed by oxidation. With the progress of further oxidation, the nucleus is attacked at the phenolic groups and is opened up forming carbon dioxide and water-soluble acids.